

The role of 6G NTN in emergency and crisis management

Carla Amatetti^{*}, Fanny Parzys[†], Laurent Reynaud[†], Sandro Scalise[‡], Alessandro Guidotti[§],
 Nicolas Chuberre[¶], Farid Benbadis^{||}, Massimo Neri^{**}, Miguel A. Vazquez^{††}, and Alessandro Vanelli-Coralli^{*}
^{*} University of Bologna Italy, [†] Orange France, [‡] DLR Germany, [§] CNIT Italy, [¶] Thales Alenia Space France,
^{||} Thales SIX GTS France, ^{**} Martel Innovate, Switzerland, ^{††} CTTC Spain

Abstract—The forthcoming generation of communication networks, known as 6G, aims to establish a 3D multi-layered network, composed of Non-Terrestrial and Terrestrial nodes, capable of delivering high throughput, low latency, and reliable services with global coverage and enhanced system availability, scalability, and resilience. Such a network offers the opportunity to revise the way organizations from Public Safety and various other Verticals provision their network connectivity to make sure they can serve anywhere, anytime, reliable and efficient communications to respond to Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) events as well as temporary unplanned events, in which the user traffic demand is expected to surge at some point in time, and exceed the capacity offered by the default terrestrial infrastructure. In this paper, we present an advanced PPDR deployment scenario based on an integrated 6G NTN architecture along with the enabling technologies that empower the 6G NTN architecture to effectively meet the requirements associated with PPDR operations. In particular, we propose a novel distributed architecture for 6G NTN networks, developed within the EC-funded project 6G-NTN. Finally, we discuss business, economical, regulatory, and governmental aspects that highly constrain the proposed architecture.

Index Terms—PPDR, 6G NTN, distributed architecture, AI

I. INTRODUCTION

As 5G networks are currently being deployed, the industries and academic communities are collaboratively defining 5G-Advanced features and identifying disruptive technologies for 6G systems [1]. These efforts aim to address the anticipated challenges for 2030 communication systems, such as achieving terabit capacity and ensuring always-on connectivity. In this context, it is widely recognized that Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN) will be essential in supporting a fully connected world, where physical, human, and digital domains converge [2], [3]. Indeed, 6G systems envision the native design and optimization of Terrestrial Networks (TNs) and NTN within a unified and fully integrated multi-layered infrastructure. This comprehensive infrastructure will combine terrestrial, airborne, and spaceborne network elements, including High Altitude Platform Systems (HAPS) and satellites [3]. The envisioned 3D multilayered architecture, illustrated in Figure 1, aims to unleash the full potential of 6G services performance in terms of availability, resilience, coverage, throughput, and service rate, by leveraging the features and operational constraints of the NTN domain from the design phase onward. Such a network offers the opportunity to revise the way organizations from Public Safety and various other Verticals provision their network connectivity to make sure they can serve anywhere,

Fig. 1. 6G-NTN 3D Network Concept [7].

anytime, reliable and efficient communications to respond to Public Protection and Disaster Relief (PPDR) events as well as temporary unplanned events, in which the user traffic demand is expected to surge at some point in time and exceed the capacity offered by the default terrestrial infrastructure. The use of satellites, drones, and HAPS for emergencies is not new in the literature [4]–[6]. In [4], the use of satellites for restoring communications in disaster-affected areas is explored, proposing several deployment scenarios that integrate the capabilities of low and geostationary earth orbit satellites with HAPS, however without providing details on the timing and methods for establishing these infrastructures. In [6], a novel architecture, made of an integrated and highly dynamic multi-purpose aerial communications infrastructure that can be contextually extended with fast-deploying high or low altitude platforms, is proposed.

With the advent of 5G technologies, the integration with satellite communications has become increasingly appealing for PPDR agencies, driven by various technology integration initiatives [8], especially the effective integration of high-throughput satellites and 5G edge computing [9]. Indeed, as noted in [10], ensuring acceptable Quality of Service (QoS) for PPDR operators during data communication is challenging without an interoperable framework between 5G and satellite communications. Therefore, the research focus has increasingly shifted towards the definition of the corresponding technical requirements for satellite communication systems to support emergency communication [11].

In this paper, we present an advanced PPDR deployment scenario based on an integrated 6G NTN architecture along with the enabling technologies that empower the 6G NTN architecture to effectively meet the requirements associated with

PPDR operations. In particular, we propose a novel distributed architecture for 6G NTN networks, developed within the EC-funded project 6G-NTN.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section II outlines the PPDR user requirements. Section III details the proposed 3D architecture for 6G NTN. In Section IV, we discuss the key enabling technologies of 6G NTN and how they can support PPDR requirements. Section V addresses non-technical challenges for 6G NTN architecture to support PPDR. Finally, Section VI concludes this paper.

II. PPDR USER REQUIREMENTS

PPDR refers to the different phases involving public safety agencies and response teams, which need to deal with events such as natural or man-made catastrophes. Despite the great diversity of deployment scenarios, depending notably on the nature of the disaster (e.g., floods, tsunamis, forest fires, hurricanes, drought, industrial catastrophes, and so on), the scale of the event and the type of involved teams, such situations generally highlight a need for efficient communications between involved personnel, at a time when existing and terrestrial infrastructures may be partially or totally damaged. In this context, and despite the great heterogeneity of first response teams' objectives, the review of typical PPDR scenarios such as [12], [13] highlights common user needs and requirements. As an example, Figure 2 (a), Figure 2 (b), and Figure 2 (c) [12] illustrate the successive stages, seen from the perspective of first responders coordination needs, of a disaster event leaving terrestrial communications infrastructure temporarily damaged. Figure 2 (b) highlights that PPDR traffic need evolves with time, while Figure 2 (c) illustrates the later stages of this PPDR scenario, in which terrestrial infrastructures are progressively repaired, implying a strong need for the restored infrastructure and the PPDR infrastructure to efficiently coexist until the terrestrial infrastructure is completely repaired. That illustrative type of deployment case allows expressing typical PPDR user needs:

- The PPDR infrastructure should be able to meet highly dynamic network coverage needs. In effect, the affected area is susceptible to change with time, due to e.g., the evolution of the considered event, or the geographical progression of responders' operations when targeting new areas.
- Rapid (or even near-instantaneous) availability of public safety connectivity is needed to accommodate the deployment timelines of the first responding teams to arrive on site.
- PPDR communication infrastructures need to scale with the changing connectivity needs of response teams, especially since, depending on their missions (e.g., emergency management, situational awareness, firefighting, rescue, maintenance of public order, infrastructure restoration, medical care, ...) they are likely to be constrained by different timelines in the way they intervene at the affected site.

Fig. 2. (a) Terrestrial infrastructure (e.g., base stations) may be left impaired by a disaster event [12] (b) Additional network resources (e.g., a high-capacity access from an aerial node) may be needed to cope with the increasing PPDR traffic [12] (c) The PPDR infrastructure may need to coexist with the repaired terrestrial infrastructure [12].

- The infrastructure should allow seamless transitions connectivity from TN and NTN segments and vice-versa, thereby allowing response teams to enter and leave disaster areas without noticeable degradation of their network experience.

A wide range of terminals are generally used in PPDR scenarios, each with its own characteristics and requirements: handheld, car-mounted, or drone-mounted devices. More particularly, aerial drones (a.k.a. UAV for Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles) have become an essential tool for search and rescue in remote areas, or in places that no human or manned vehicle

can reach. They can quickly patrol over vast territories and significantly speed up the evaluation of damage and organization of adequate emergency response. Through aerial photos, videos, or night vision data transmitted in real-time, they help identify safe places, locate survivors, and even deliver first relief to the trapped populations. Drones have been used, for example, in April 2015, when Nepal experienced one of its most terrible earthquakes in its recent history. Today, in most emergency situations, a drone is controlled manually by a remote pilot, for example using the FPV mode (First Person view or immersive flight, thanks to a camera). In this case, link availability and low latency become vital, to ensure flight reactivity and avoid losing the drone. However, the current situation is still a practice suffering from several drawbacks. First, the propagation range of communication links used today limits drone operations to the areas that can be reached by the pilot. Second, there is usually no backhaul connection to a cloud for data processing, such that image analysis can be only performed manually, by first responders located with the pilot. This clearly limits operations coordination between teams and prevents the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for autonomous detection. Future 6G NTN technologies could bring key benefits to search and rescue drones:

- The low latency of NTN links would enable the use of satellite communications even for manual drone control, thus achieving ubiquitous drone services. A maximum latency (round-trip, from drone to controller and back to drone) of 150ms is preferred, ideally 100ms especially in bad weather conditions or complex and dense environments (such as collapsed buildings or forests).
- The link versatility of an integrated TN / NTN system, together with the ability to seamlessly switch from one network to another one (even while in communication), would make drone services unaffected by the evolution of the PPDR communication infrastructures (activated tactical bubble, NTN unavailable due to clouds, recovery of the public TN, etc.) or by the constraints of the field of operations (e.g., navigating through debris of destroyed buildings, etc.). Seamless switching is envisaged in the horizontal plane (to cope with potential gaps in the terrestrial infrastructure), but also in the vertical plane (i.e. leaving terrestrial coverage due to altitude). Predicting link quality and potential service interruptions could greatly enhance remote control of drones. This capability would enable the drone to switch to a safe or autonomous flight mode proactively, thereby mitigating risks associated with fluctuating connectivity between TN and NTN.
- The ability to quickly process and interpret drone-captured data to make informed decisions is essential. LIDAR or high-definition videos are often considered. Such streams are typically uplink and around some tens of Mbps (reaching up to 200 Mbps for some specialized scenarios). Space edge computing would also advantageously provide an ubiquitous cloud access, even when

Fig. 3. Distributed architecture for LEO constellation [7].

terrestrial infrastructure is damaged.

- 3D reliable positioning without Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) would also significantly support PPDR drone services.
- Compact unified TN / NTN terminals are a valuable advantage for drone integration.

III. 6G NTN ARCHITECTURE

In this section, we describe the 6G NTN architecture proposed in the 6G-NTN project. In particular, this architecture is designed to provide very high throughput, low latency, and reliable services, which are essential features in addressing the aforementioned requirements of PPDR users and in the deployment of drones for search and rescue. As previously mentioned, the underpinning concept of 6G NTN is a 3D multi-layered architecture [7], illustrated in Figure 1. The “3D” characteristic stems from the full integration of the non-terrestrial component with the terrestrial one, while the “multi-layered” feature is related to the integration of different layers consisting of communication nodes, i.e., satellites or HAPs flying at different and multiple altitudes. The flying nodes are interconnected by inter-node links (INL). We categorize the connections within this system into two types: horizontal links, which connect nodes within the same constellation, such as Low Earth Orbit (LEO) to LEO, and vertical links, which connect nodes across different constellations, such as LEO to Geostationary Earth Orbit (GEO). The differentiation between horizontal and vertical links plays a significant role in the definition of the architecture interfaces as the characteristics (e.g., delay, availability, etc) of the links change significantly. The 6G NTN topology considers two types of non-terrestrial nodes, namely deterministic nodes with a fixed and predictable orbit (both Geostationary (GSO) and Non-GSO (NGSO)) and flexible nodes, namely HAPS or special heavy drones, which might or might not be present at different points in time and at different locations to extend coverage or enhance the network capacity. The latter are supposed to be deployed “opportunistically” depending on specific needs and they are not meant to be a permanent infrastructure with global coverage. Indeed, the flexible nodes need to ensure additional coverage to the deterministic coverage to: i) enhance locally the capacities (to

fulfill a gap or infrastructure failure, natural disasters, etc.); ii) to fulfill new requests and support market evolution; and iii) to face a failure. It is worth mentioning that these kinds of nodes, deployed at an altitude in the range 18-25 km, shall be integrated into the 6G NTN network at any place on the earth [14]. One of the most innovative features currently under further investigation and consolidation in the 6G-NTN project is that of a distributed architecture for the NGSO constellation. In contrast to all existing constellations, the satellites are, in this case, not all identical in terms of payload hardware and functionalities. Specifically, we distinguish between service satellites and feeder satellites. As illustrated in Figure 3, service satellites are exclusively dedicated to provide connectivity to UEs and do not incorporate feeder links. Consequently, the payload mass and power resources are allocated to optimize service uplink and downlink capacities. These service satellites establish connections with feeder satellites via Inter-Satellite Links (ISLs), but they lack feeder links and do not have ISLs between one another. Conversely, feeder satellites do not have direct links to UEs and instead establish the transport network in space through the use of ISLs and feeder links. In addition, they offer enhanced processing capabilities in space to support radio access network (RAN) functions, and if required, Core Network and Edge Computing functionalities. This architectural approach offers several notable advantages, including:

- increased service link throughput as resources in the service satellites are exclusively allocated to service links rather than shared with feeder links and ISLs. Consequently, the full available power and mass can be dedicated to enhance service link performance and associated hardware, such as power amplifiers and beamforming networks;
- enhanced scalability and flexibility since feeder satellites operate independently of the spectrum and bandwidth used for service links. Provided that the capacity of ISLs and feeder links does not become a limiting factor, new service satellites (more powerful and/or operating in a different frequency band) can be incrementally and seamlessly integrated into the system.

Basically, through the distributed architecture the service links are completely decoupled from the transport network in space. Although this concept is not new, so far it has been considered mostly at academic level. As a matter of fact, all existing constellations, including e.g., Starlink (if we exclude the fact that different generations are coexisting in space) adopt a conventional design where all satellites are (almost) identical from a hardware point of view and include both service and feeder links. It shall be noted that the proposed solution requires ca 15% more satellites and additional payload design and accommodation. This will be analyzed in the cost assessment to be performed in the remaining part of the 6G-NTN project. In terms of RAN functions, the idea is to have the full gNB in space (to reduce latency, especially on the control plane) but split it between service and feeder satellites, from

Fig. 4. LLS based NTN architecture enabling also routing of traffic between feeder satellites [7].

which the name of “distributed architecture” actually stems. Feeder satellites shall implement the baseband unit (BBU) functionality, whereas the service satellites shall carry a radio unit (RU) and provide the service link to the user terminals on the ground. For the sake of clarity, “baseband” includes the whole upper layers of the radio protocol stack while the lower (physical) layer processing functionalities are split between the feeder satellite and the service satellites. Such split between baseband unit and radio unit is known as the lower layer split (LLS) where the O-LLS is the Open-RAN (ORAN) standardized version of such a split [15]. Assuming each feeder satellite can serve a cluster of 4 service satellites, Figure 4 shows how the switch/router in the feeder satellite can be used to route the backhaul from the feeder link to another feeder satellite in a neighboring cluster. Some of the aspects that motivate this concept are that power budget and payloads can be optimized for the different roles of the satellites. One potential downside of this solution is that no centralized scheduling will be possible as each feeder satellite will have its own scheduler. The system could, on the other hand, support slower radio resource management coordination, such as is done in terrestrial networks.

Last but not least, the ISLs between service and feeder satellites become a key element, both in terms of reliability (given that service satellites have no feeder links and feeder satellites have no service links) as well as in terms of bandwidth, since the LLS result in a certain bandwidth expansion on the fronthaul links. A realistically estimated bandwidth expansion factor, which shall be considered when dimensioning the ISLs is between 5-10 [7].

IV. 6G NTN KEY ENABLING TECHNOLOGIES

In Section II, we identified several 6G NTN technologies, including 3D reliable positioning independent of GNSS, compact unified terminals, and space edge computing, all of which hold significant promise for enhancing search and rescue drone capabilities. Building on this foundation, we now examine additional features of the 6G NTN network that serve as key enablers for PPDR operations.

- Flexible software defined payload: a virtualization concept for the payload functionality allows the optimization of the platform and payload resources’ usage, especially in the framework of an emergency situation. Such a new conceptual approach to the satellite’s payload design

requires two main enhancements on the space segment and terrestrial architectural definition: i) an on-board capacity allowing to virtualize part or all payload usual physical resources', e.g., memory, storage, computation, beam steering; ii) the partial or total virtualization of the NTN functionalities under one or several virtual network functions (VNFs), either in the space segment, or /and in the terrestrial segment. Therefore, an NTN payload could be built around more generic hardware or software components associated with generic software frameworks, hosting virtualized capabilities orchestrated under cloud computing techniques, such as Network as a Service, or Infrastructure as a Service. Immediate benefits will be, for instance, the smart and flexible management of all radio resources spread over the space segment in the same way as it is done on ground (relying on Software Defined Radio – SDR- technologies), on-board packet processing for smart applications (including routing, traffic analysis, optimization of the network configuration, etc.), and flexible orchestration of virtual network functions. This will enable high reconfigurability (frequency plan, connectivity, beam hopping pattern) and high re-programmability (small scale) for PPDR, governmental, and professional applications requiring meshed configurations.

- Cloud native architecture: the essence of 6G NTN architecture lies in its inherent ability to dynamically orchestrate resources, intelligently allocating and re-allocating computing, storage, and networking assets in real-time. Central to this architecture is the concept of autonomy. By leveraging cutting-edge technologies such as AI and Machine Learning (ML), autonomous monitoring mechanisms continuously observe network performance, identify anomalies, and proactively take corrective actions. This proactive approach not only enhances network reliability and robustness but also minimizes downtime and service disruptions, ensuring a seamless and uninterrupted user experience. Within this framework, container orchestration in cloud environments, utilizing standardized interfaces, empowers rapid prototyping of new services and accelerates the iteration of novel solutions. Thus, the 6G NTN orchestrator must be designed to collect real-time information from the core network, obtain traffic forecasts, and assess hardware resource requirements through AI techniques that predict future network conditions. Based on this intelligence, the orchestrator can make adaptive and dynamic decisions for the core network, deploying VNFs and edge services on physical nodes as necessary, improving response times and saving bandwidth. In [16], an example of a dynamic VNFs orchestrator solution for 6G NTN is thoroughly described.

In the context of PPDR, a cloud-native architecture would facilitate the activation and placement of AI functions—such as prioritization in resource allocation—based on geographic position and resource availability, e.g., computational resources. This capability en-

ables the deployment of critical services close to the emergency area, enhancing the effectiveness and responsiveness of PPDR operations.

- AI-enhanced RAN controller: the effort to efficiently use the resources in 6G NTN is becoming a priority, both in non-real Time (non-RT) and near Real Time (n-RT), especially under emergency situations. Indeed, it is of paramount importance to enhance the overall system performance while providing reliable and cost-effective services. The significance of this requirement arises for the multi-orbital and multi-band satellite integrated networks that introduce complexities due to the variability of satellite links, non-uniform traffic demand, dynamic user densities with time, and heterogeneous channel conditions. Thus, efficient Radio Resource Management (RRM) can be achieved through intelligent decision-making for available throughput capacity, spectrum usage, and mitigating interference to enhance overall network performance. In the framework of an emergency or unplanned situation, the 6G NTN network can enable the rapid optimization of the exploitation of the resources in the emergency area. This optimization can be achieved at: i) at the single gNB level, i.e., by changing the RAN resource, such as the bandwidth allocated to a specific user or group of users; the transmission power of the gNB, the beam hopping pattern, and the precoding coefficients to enhance the coverage in a disaster area; or ii) at the system level by distributing the users among the available gNBs (terrestrial and non-terrestrial) in the impacted area [17]. Examples of AI-based network functions advancements in NTN aspects that are partially explored or yet to be explored in RRM are [18], [19]: i) Cell Load Balancing; ii) Fractional Frequency Reuse; iii) Traffic Prediction; iv) Link Quality Prediction.
- Flexible unified waveform: as 6G development will integrate NTN from the beginning, there is the potential for optimizing the design of the waveform, making the waveform "NTN-friendly". In this context, the desired features of waveform design should include [20]: i) the compatibility with terrestrial networks to facilitate seamless handover between TN and NTNs, ensuring seamless connectivity for users moving between different coverage areas or network types. This feature promotes device compatibility, i.e., enabling devices to operate seamlessly across both TN and NTNs without necessitating significant modifications or additional hardware (i.e., using the same chipset), thereby enhancing user experience and device versatility. ii) A flexible waveform also ensures continuous and reliable connectivity for UE across diverse deployment scenarios and geographical regions, regardless of the type or location of the NTN platform being accessed. A well-designed waveform for NTN facilitates seamless connectivity by enabling a seamless transition between TN and NTN, thus ensuring a good end-user experience throughout the coverage area. iii) A third fundamental feature is the support of accurate

network-based positioning to facilitate robust localization capabilities, allowing network operators to accurately track the geographic locations of UE devices for various applications, such as emergency services, location-based services, and network optimization. This could entail, for example, the provision of dedicated pilot symbols or reference signals within the waveform to enable precise timing and phase measurements for accurate estimation of UE positions. Furthermore, waveform parameters, such as symbol duration, subcarrier spacing, and transmission power levels, can be carefully optimized to balance between localization accuracy and spectral efficiency.

iv) Finally backward compatibility with 5G ensures that 6G NTN can leverage the infrastructure, devices, and protocols established by 5G deployments. By maintaining backward compatibility, the air interface promotes immediate compatibility with 5G smartphones and devices, enabling efficient utilization of existing network resources and enhancing the user experience across both 5G and 6G networks.

V. NON-TECHNICAL CHALLENGES FOR THE 6G NTN ARCHITECTURE TO SUPPORT PPDR USER REQUIREMENTS

So far, we have considered technical features for supporting PPDR scenarios in 6G-NTN. However, the discussed architecture is highly constrained by business, economical, regulatory, and governmental aspects. First, the proposed system must be economically viable. As PPDR scenarios are (fortunately!) occasional, it is necessary to pair this infrastructure with other commercial usage, to ensure sufficient revenues and compensate for the deployment and operation costs. This is particularly true for HAPS, which still fails to find the right economical balance as analyzed in [21]. However, such studies do not consider the flexible integration of HAPS into a larger 6G NTN architecture, which is likely to dilute higher HAP cost structure into a more favorable NTN economic equation, while at the same time keeping the benefits of contextually using HAP systems, as formerly illustrated by Figure 2 (b).

From that perspective, drones used as flying network access points offer a cheaper and quick-to-deploy solution, but come with many challenges as well. Given their relatively low altitude, they only offer restricted coverage (< a few kms) and better suit local dead spots. A trade-off between service continuity and interference management must be found. In particular, using unlicensed spectrum (e.g., WiFi) simplifies radio planning but hardly offers integrated PPDR services, accessible with off-the-shelf user devices. In addition, the need for a backhaul link adds significant deployment and regulation constraints. Last but not least, battery consumption still remains the major restriction and to maintain coverage over time, tethered drones connected to a transportable power supply are more appropriate. The proposed 6G NTN system potentially leverages these drawbacks thanks to flexible resource management and optimized multi-connectivity. Next, responses to large-scale disasters often gather first responders from different countries and organizations, which can

be public, private, governmental or non-governmental, local, national, international, etc. In addition, PPDR services can be shared by several countries, for economical sustainability. Thus, an essential feature of the PPDR system is fair resource sharing and trusted identity and authorization management. This is also about security, as PPDR infrastructure cannot be a weak point in accessing vital network infrastructures, services, and cloud.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we presented an advanced PPDR deployment scenario that relies on the 6G NTN architecture and its key technologies, such as a flexible software-defined payload, a cloud-native architecture, an AI-enhanced RAN controller, and a flexible unified waveform. The 6G NTN architecture is based on innovative concepts called 'distributed' architecture, where the LEO satellites are categorized into service and feeder satellites. The former provides services to the users and does not have a feeder link and ISLs with other service satellites; while the latter has a feeder link and ISL with the service satellites, but is not directly connected to the users. This approach allow to increase the service link throughput, to enhance scalability and flexibility of the network, and to dedicate part of the feeder satellite payload resources to edge computing functionalities. All of them are fundamental features to meet the PPDR user requirements along with the introduced key technologies.

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